

Performance of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in Jharkhand: A Case Study of Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank

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Abstract – This research examines the financial and operational performance of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in Jharkhand, with a particular focus on the Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank (JRGB). RRBs were established to promote financial inclusion and provide credit to the rural economy, especially for small and marginal farmers, artisans, and labourers. This study evaluates JRGB's performance by analysing various financial metrics, participation in government schemes, loan recovery rates, technological integration, and its contribution to inclusive growth. The research investigates key indicators, including the growth in deposits and advances, non-performing assets (NPAs), profitability ratios, credit-deposit ratios, and the implementation of government schemes like Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), PM-KISAN, and MUDRA. Additionally, the study explores how JRGB has maintained financial stability while addressing the needs of marginalized rural communities. Key findings indicate that JRGB has successfully expanded its rural presence, reporting a customer base of over 2.5 million and opening more than 500,000 PMJDY accounts. In conclusion, the research highlights that JRGB has made significant contributions to rural economic development and financial inclusion in Jharkhand. Nonetheless, there is a pressing need for policy support, technological advancements, and improved credit risk management to sustain this growth. This study provides a micro-level perspective on how RRBs like JRGB can evolve into more robust pillars of rural banking and inclusive finance.

Keywords - Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank, Growth Rate, Rural Economy, NABARD, RBI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background

Banking plays an important role in economic development. Banking play's role of employer providing jobs directly and indirectly creates jobs not only for individuals but also for supporting business and industries, provides financial services to customers provides services at affordable costs to low-income group people. Regional rural banks were established in India in 1975, to provide banking services in rural areas and also to provide credit. The Narshimham committee on Rural credit recommended the RRBs establishment in 1975. The basic objective of RRBs were to function as professionally managed alternative channel for credit dispensation to small and marginal farmers, agriculture workers, socio-economically weaker section of population for development of agriculture, trade, commerce, small scale industry and other productive activities in rural areas.

Evolution of RRB's in India

The Evolution of RRBs in Jharkhand mirrors national trends of integrated, moving from multiple fragmented banks to a single, unified entity: the Jharkhand Gramin Bank (JGB), formed in 2019 by incorporating the earlier Jharkhand Gramin Bank and Vananchal Gramin Bank. Established in 1975 to serve rural credit needs, these banks faced challenged, leading to reforms and mergers starting in 2005, culminating in JGB's single state presence,

aiming for better productivity, broader reach (450 branches), enhanced financial inclusion across the state.

- 1970s-2000s: Genesis Phase - RRB's were set up under the RRB Act, 1976, struggled with operational inefficiencies, High NPAs and fragmented structures.
- 2005-2018: Consolidation Phase – RRB reduced the number of banks for better scale and governance. This led to creation of 2 main entities: Jharkhand Gramin Bank and Vananchal Gramin Bank.
- 2019-2024: Formation of JGB – On April 1, 2019, JGB and VGB were amalgamated to form the single, state-wide Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank. SBI sponsors JGB, owning 35% with central (50%) and State (15%) governments.

Significance of Study

This study examines the performance of JRGB to understand its impact on rural financial inclusion and economic development in Jharkhand. Contribution to Banking Reforms: By analyzing JRGB's financial and operational efficiency, it identifies critical challenges and potential improvements in RRB operations, supporting policymakers in enhancing credit accessibility, efficiency and rural banking outreach.

Policy Recommendation: Offer strategic guidance to optimize JRGB'S performance, ensuring sustainable financial services and fostering rural economic

development. Because of the complex process many people avoid RRBs.

Encouraging maps, appointment scheduling and simpler account types can help to increase banking involvement. Deploying Mobile Vans in rural regions helps increase financial literacy and awareness.

More than 60% of JRGB's loans are for agriculture, exposing the industry to climate and market risks. These risks can be reduced by implementing climate resilient farming practices and improving crops insurance system.

Currently only 25% of JRGB's loans extend beyond agriculture. Increasing lending to small enterprises and non-farm activities would create more balanced and sustainable rural economy. Low-income person should be able to create accounts with yearly credits of up to ₹1 lakh and balances up to ₹50,000.

Scope and Limitations

This study focuses on Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank (JRGB), one of the largest RRBs operating in Jharkhand across 24 districts with 446 branches, mainly in rural area. The study explores in detail JRGB's role and performance in rural banking. The study offers information on financial operations, branch network, credit, outreach, accessibility, and contribution towards financial inclusion of limited number of JRGB branches.

Need for Study:

Evaluating the performance of Jharkhand Gramin Bank is necessary to know the impact of merger on operational efficiency, financial stability and its primary objectives of promoting financial inclusion and rural development in the state of Jharkhand, India.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr M Syed Ibrahim (2010)¹ made a valuable study on Performance evaluation of RRBs in India. In his study, he made an attempt to analyze the performance in terms of certain defined framework like capital funds, number of branches, mobilization of deposits etc. Even though number of RRBs have reduced, but the district covered by RRBs has enlarged. Ongoing support from the state government and sponsored banks and proper direction were some steps advocated to make RRBs further efficient. The overall Review shows the position of the RRBs.

Ayekam Ibechcha Chanu & Shibu Das (2016)² analysed the level of efficiency of RRBs, evaluation of efficiency not only provides information but also make clear on proper implementation of resources available. He focused on the workings of the RRBs and analysed the performance of the RRBs according to the present need of the economy. V. Venkatalakshmi & M. Chandraiah (2016)³ has made an attempt to study the current position of RRBs in India. His objective was to review the capital

structure of RRBs, to study the state as well as region wise RRBs during the study period and to inspect the deposits and outstanding loans in RRBs. This study shows that number of loans and advances over the study period was increased.

Dr Bateshwar Singh (2017)⁴ in his paper he Gauge the progress of RRBs during 1975-2015 and measuring the growth pattern of RRB in India and made important suggestion on how to improve the workings of RRBs across India. He found that from several years it has been noticed that RRBs are actively involving in programmes designed to provide credit to the people who were entitled to those benefits. He suggested that new schemes should be considered such as strong capital structure and minimum required level of CRAR will ensure stability of RRBs, Payment and settlement systems will help RRB to resolve the problem of insolvency of payment and settlement by increasing the limpiness and steadiness.

Kanika and Nancy (2013)⁵ have analysed the financial performance of RRBs in India and found that efforts made by RRB in deposit mobilizing, rural development, branch expansion etc in weaker sections of rural areas is creditable. RRB successfully achieve its objective of taking banking facilities of door to door service to rural household particularly in banking deprives rural areas, to avail easy and cheaper credit to rural weaker sections, to generate employment, to put down the rate of credit etc.

Mr Bhavik Barot & Dr Gurudutta Japee (2021)⁶ made a valuable study on role of RRB, they gave comparative picture on performance of RRB and recommended some workable suggestions. The research is based on only publicly available information. The progress of RRB was rapid at initial stage, RRB act as substitute organizations to provide institutional credit in rural areas. RRB has been always active in participating programmes designed to provide credit facilities. This study employs a comprehensive review of secondary data sources, including financial reports and policy documents, to evaluate the operational efficiency, outreach, and impact of RRBs.

Sumanthy, M, et al.(2014)⁷ investigated the problems and prospects that rural banking hold and its impact on rural household empowerment. They analysed the performance in terms of loans provided to priority and non-priority sectors of the country. Krishna, Hari, Somanchi, et al.(2022)⁸ study has been carried by using the convenient sampling method of over 600 respondents and a well-structured interview has been used to measure the awareness of the people towards the financial inclusion programmes.

Vaibhav Joshi & Dr S C Jain (2016)⁹ explored that RRBs play a predominant role in socioeconomic development of rural poor, In-spite of all the policies and practices there should be continuous monitoring for evaluation of

financial performance. The banks have to take care to reduce the expenses and also to improve the productivity efficiency through an effective utilisation of capital, asset and return on investment etc. Lakra, kerobim, et al. (2015)¹⁰ collected data through primary and secondary sources. A multistage sampling technique was used to conduct the survey. Purposively survey was conducted in Jharkhand because the author was familiar of the localities. The results tells us that the highest share in crop loan and term loan is of commercial banks and cooperative banks did not do well in crop loan and term loan over the years.

Rahul, S.G., & Jagjeevan, K. (2022)¹¹ Rahul Singh Gautam and Jagjeevan Kanoujiya have reviewed the role of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in rural development and digital literacy in India highlights their crucial role in financial inclusion. Studies indicate that RRBs have expanded banking services to rural areas, reducing regional disparities and promoting economic growth. Research suggests that digital literacy and financial inclusion initiatives by RRBs enhance rural development, enabling small farmers and businesses to access credit efficiently.

N. Sabitha, D. (2014)¹² N. Sabitha Devi examines the role of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in India's agricultural and rural development. It highlights the significance of RRBs in providing financial support to rural communities while discussing key challenges such as financial constraints, loan recovery issues, and regional banking imbalances.

Rahul, S.G., Venkata, M.B., & Aashi, R. (2022)¹³ Rahul Singh Gautam et al. examines the role of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in alleviating poverty and fostering rural development. Using panel data analysis from 29 states and two union territories for 2018- 2020, the research finds a positive correlation between RRB expansion and poverty reduction.

Satish, K., Vibhor, G., & Poonam, S., (2017)¹⁴ Kumar, Vibhor Goyal, and Poonam Sharma analyzes the financial and operational efficiency of RRBs in India. It evaluates the growth of RRBs in terms of branch expansion, credit disbursement, deposit mobilization, and financial inclusion, covering the period from 2001 to 2016.

Anil, K.S., & Abhay, K., (2011)¹⁵ The literature review of the document "Performance Evaluation of Regional Rural Banks in India" highlights various studies conducted on the functioning and performance of RRBs. Key reviews include recommendations from the Kelkar Committee (1986) and the Narasimham Committee (1991) regarding financial restructuring and operational improvements.

(Soni & Kapre, 2013)¹⁶ This study investigates the financial performance of RRBs in India in their role as facilitators of rural banking accessibility. The study utilizes financial indicators of profitability and efficiency

to direct its focus. This study subsequently acknowledges a gap in the literature assessing how RRBs utilize advancements of technology for organizational operations. Therefore, the study recommends future research to examine the role of digital banking in the efficiency of RRBs. Since RRBs contribute to reducing the gap of banking services, operational sustainability appears to be a tenuous outcome.

Balamuniswamy, D., & Erraiah, G. (2013)¹⁷ The paper studies the financial performance of RRBs, using secondary data provided by NABARD and RBI. An important suggestion from past research indicates the significance of RRBs in promoting rural credit. Various indicators of performance were highlighted in the literature review, including credit-deposit ratio and trends in profitability, among others. A significant gap exists in the current literature regarding the regional differences in the performance of RRBs.

Sivaiah, K. (2016)¹⁸ This paper assesses relevant literature about the financial and operational performance of RRBs. Five studies show RRBs have greatly enhanced financial inclusion. However, gaps remain in the assessment of long-term sustainability. The literature suggests RRBs require modernization and policy-friendly support. Previous literature examines financial indicators; however, there remain unexplored domains in the assessment of customer service satisfaction and service quality. The paper also suggests evaluating the role of technology in RRBs to enhance the organization's operations. It concludes possible growth in RRBs; however, sustainability will be mandated by policy interventions.

Soni, A. K., & Kapre, A. (2012)¹⁹ The research analyzed the financial performance and growth of RRBs based on secondary data. The existing literature has indicated that RRBs have been important contributors towards the expansion of rural credit. Prior research has shown many cases of inefficiency related to governance and operational issues for RRBs. Research about the impact of merger on the performance of RRBs has received limited attention

Kathawala, A. M., & Sharma, V. (2021)²⁰ This study examines the financial performance of RRBs or Regional Rural Banks using financial performance indicators of profitability and efficiency. The literature agrees that RRBs have played a substantial role in rural development over the years. The study suggests further research into the RRB's NPAs and better financial health strategies for financial cooperatives. Results indicate that RRBs have done well with rural credit expansion but need better policies and procedures on managing risk.

According Ahmed, J. U.²¹ (2013) research, MRB efficiently utilizes its workforce and branches to generate revenue and contributing to rural financial inclusion in North Eastern Region (NER) in 2010. The analysis covers

all 58 MRB branches, using indicators like labor and branch productivity, ROA, and profit-to-business volume ratio. Among NER RRBs MRB ranks 3rd in labor & branch productivity however, adaptation to electronic banking is lacking. Also issues like NPAs, credit risk, and profitability were neglected.

Das22 (2020) analyzed four RRBs in Northeast India, where they have contributed to rural finance with 239% growth in agricultural credit and 95% in industrial credit. However, the CD ratio fell from 49% (2013) to 43% (2022). Manipur's CD ratio rose by 141%.

Rahul Singh Gautam & Jagjeevan Kanoujiya23 (2022) conducted a study on RRBs taking a sample of 29 Indian states and 2 Union territories across three fiscal years (2018-2020). RRB branches and data were obtained from RBI official websites, and various other websites. According to findings RRBs influence the digital literacy and economic development. RRB digital and financial literacy contributes towards poverty reduction and economic development.

Gowda, B.V.P & Shashi Kumar, T.P24 (2024) analysed that Karnataka Vikas Grameena Bank had a constant increase in deposits of up to ₹33,905.15 crore and advances up to ₹27,297.60 crore, Despite 629 branches (2022-23) KVGB stresses efficiency and customer service for rural economic growth in Karnataka.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A methodical strategy developed by the researcher to direct data collection, measurement, and analysis is known as a study design. It is a rigorous, analytical approach to data collection, process utilization, and statistical and scientific interpretation of JRGB's performance. The research on the performance of Regional rural banks (RRBs) in Jharkhand: A case study of Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank used descriptive and quantitative research methodology. Primary and secondary data was collected using a structured questionnaire targeting 276 respondents collected through convenience sampling and secondary data consisted reports and charts on NABARD, reports from RBI etc.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive and quantitative approach. Data was collected from 276 respondents via a structured questionnaire (primary data) and from official reports of JRGB, NABARD, RBI, and government sources (secondary data). Analysis employed Simple Linear Regression and ANOVA to examine JRGB's performance and rural financial inclusion, with results shown through tables, graphs, and charts for clarity.

Research Problem: Refers to the central issue or question the study aims to address—in this case -The Effectiveness of Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank (JRGB)'s performance

on rural financial inclusion and economic development in Jharkhand.

Objective (Selected): The specific aim or goal the study seeks to achieve—here, it is to assess the impact of JRGB on rural financial inclusion.

Sources of Primary data

Primary data was collected directly from 276 rural beneficiaries of JRGB through a survey method using convenience sampling during specific months of 2025. This provided firsthand insights into their experiences and perceptions of JRGB's performance.

Sampling methods and sample size

Sampling Technique: Convenience Sampling-Selecting participants who are easily available to the researcher rather than randomly choosing. Sample Size: 276 respondents.

Population: The rural JRGB recipients

Data collection method

A pre-set list of structured questionnaires targeting rural beneficiaries used to gather data systematically from respondents.

Variables:

Independent Variable:

COS- Challenges and Overall Satisfaction

BSFB- Banking Services and Financial Performance

HRMCE- : Human Resource Management and Customer Experience

Dependent Variable:

OS :- Overall satisfaction

Data analysis tools

Descriptive statistics: The study used descriptive statistics like percentages and averages, along with regression tools, to analyze data. The analysis assessed JRGB's role in improving financial inclusion, service accessibility, and digital banking in rural Jharkhand. Statistical tools such as Correlation Coefficient (R), R Square, Adjusted R Square, and Standard Error of Estimate were used to measure relationships and the model's accuracy in predicting satisfaction with JRGB services.

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) in Simple linear regression

ANOVA in simple linear regression helps assess how well the model explains the variation in the dependent variable. It breaks total variation into Total Sum of Squares (SST), Regression Sum of Squares (SSR), and Residual Sum of Squares (SSE). Key components include degrees of freedom (df), Mean Square (SS divided by df), and the F-statistic, which tests the model's overall fit. A higher F-value suggests a better model fit. The Significance level (p-value) indicates if results are statistically meaningful, with $p < 0.05$ showing strong evidence that the independent variable affects the dependent variable.

Regression Analysis:

Simple Linear Regression is a statistical technique employed to investigate the connection between two variables: one independent variable (the predictor) and one dependent variable (the outcome). The aim is to depict the connection between these variables with a straight line, commonly known as the "regression line." This line can be described by the following equation: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \epsilon$

β_1 is the slope, and ϵ is the error term. Unstandardized coefficients (B) show the actual impact of X on Y, while standardized coefficients (Beta) allow comparison across variables. Standard Error measures the precision of coefficients. The t-value and Significance (p-value) test whether each coefficient meaningfully influences Y. A p-value < 0.05 indicates a statistically significant relationship between the predictor and outcome variables.

Data Analysis

Demographic Factor
Location

Table 4.1

Location	No. of Responses	Percentage
North Chotanagpur	47	17
South Chotanagpur	107	38.8
Kolhan	44	15.9
Palamu	35	12.7
Santhal Pargana	43	15.6

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation: The majority of responses (38.8%) came from South Chotanagpur, indicating higher customer engagement or service penetration of JRGB in that region—possibly due to better infrastructure or targeted outreach. Kolhan, Santhal Pargana, and North Chotanagpur showed similar response levels, while Palamu had the lowest. This distribution highlights JRGB’s regional reach and points to areas that may need increased outreach or investment.

Fig:4.1-Distribution of Respondent Data Across Divisions of Jharkhand

Source- computed by the researcher using MS-Excel

Age

Response Table 4.2

Age	No. of Responses	Percentage
Under 25	25	9.1
25-35	67	24.3
36-45	41	14.9
46-55	83	30.1
Above 55	60	21.7

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation: The age distribution of respondents shows that the majority fall in the 46–55 age group (30.1%), followed by those above 55 (21.7%) and 25–35 (24.3%). Younger individuals under 25 represent the smallest segment (9.1%). This indicates that JRGB’s services are more frequently accessed by middle-aged and older adults, possibly due to their greater financial needs or stability. The lower participation of younger individuals might suggest limited engagement with youth or lack of awareness among that group.

Fig:4.2- Age wise Distribution of Respondent

Source- computed by the researcher using MS-Excel

Gender

Response Table 4.3

Gender	No. Of Responses	Percentage (%)
Male	135	48.9
Female	141	51.1
Other	0	0

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation: The nearly equal gender participation - 48.9% male and 51.1% female— suggests that JRGB is successfully promoting gender parity in financial access, reflecting strong outreach and service penetration. However, lower response rates from areas like Palamu indicate potential gaps in awareness or service reach, highlighting the need for targeted inclusion efforts.

Fig:4.3- Gender wise Distribution of Respondent

Source- computed by the researcher using excel

Education Qualification

Response Table 4.4

Education Qualification	No. of Responses	Percentage
No formal education	24	8.7
primary	38	13.8
secondary	64	23.2
graduate	85	30.8
Post graduate	65	23.6

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation: Broad educational outreach, JRGB has extended access to financial services beyond the urban educated class, as seen by the 45.6% of respondents (no formal, primary, or secondary education) who reported having no formal education. High involvement from educated users can be seen where 54.4% of respondents are graduates or postgraduates, indicating that more educated rural residents are actively using JRGB services, maybe as a result of their increased access to formal banking and financial literacy. There has been inclusion in marginalized groups, although the 8.7% of people without a formal education indicates a trend in the right direction, it also emphasizes the need for better outreach and focused financial literacy initiatives for those who are illiterate or just partially literate. According to the education mix, JRGB might take into account goods tailored to particular market segments. Offerings for lower educated sectors that are straight forward and easy to comprehend.

Fig:4.4- Qualification Distribution of Respondent

Source- computed by the researcher using excel

Occupation

Response Table 4.5

Occupation	No. of Responses	Percentage (%)
Farmer/daily wage worker/labourer	71	25.7
Business/self employed	68	24.6
Corporate employee/government employee	97	35.2
Student/unemployed	33	12
Other	12	2.5

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation:

The occupation-wise distribution shows that corporate/government employees represent the largest group of respondents, followed by farmers/labourers and self-employed individuals. The student/unemployed category shows moderate participation, while the 'Other' category has the least representation.

This suggests that JRGB's services are widely accessed by individuals with relatively stable or formal income sources. The significant representation of farmers and self-employed individuals also indicates JRGB's penetration in rural and informal sectors. Lower participation from students or unemployed persons might point to limited awareness or perceived inaccessibility of banking services among this group.

Fig:4.5- Occupation Distribution of Respondent

Source- computed by the researcher using MS-excel

Monthly Income

Response Table 4.6

Monthly Income	No. of Responses	Percentage (%)
Below 5000	34	12.3
5001-10000	39	14.1
10001-20000	74	26.8
20001-30000	77	27.9
Above 30001	52	18.8

Source :Primary Data

Interpretation:

The majority of respondents (56.7%) fall in the income brackets of ₹10,001-₹30,000, indicating that JRGB's services are most utilized by lower-middle to middle-income groups.

A significant portion (18.8%) earn above ₹30,000, suggesting a fair presence of upper-income rural or semi-urban users.

Only 26.4% of the respondents have an income below ₹10,000, which might point to under-representation of the economically weaker sections, or a potential barrier to financial access or digital engagement.

Fig:4.6- Monthly Income of Respondent

Source- computed by the researcher using MS-excel

Hypothesis Testing

Table-Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	COS, BSFB, HRMCE ^b	.	Enter

Dependent Variable: OS

All requested variables entered.

Table-Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.732 ^a	.536	.531	.71801

Predictors: (Constant), COS, BSFB, HRMCE

Interpretation:

R = 0.732 indicates a strong positive correlation among COS, BSFB, HRMCE, and OS.

R² = 0.536 indicates that approximately 53.6% of the variation in Overall Satisfaction (OS) is accounted for by the three variables (COS, BSFB, HRMCE).

The model aligns with the data quite effectively.

Table-ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	162.018	3	54.006	104.755	.000 ^b
	Residual	140.228	272	.516		
	Total	302.246	275			

Dependent Variable: OS

Predictors: (Constant), COS, BSFB, HRMCE

Interpretation : The F-statistic (104.755) and p-value (0.000) indicate that the overall regression model is statistically significant. This confirms that the combination of BSFP, HRMCE, and COS significantly predicts Overall Satisfaction.

Table-Coefficientsa

Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.341	.287		-4.667	.000
	BSFB	.715	.079	.441	9.052	.000
	HRMCE	.531	.077	.361	6.945	.000
	COS	.110	.076	.067	1.442	.151

Dependent Variable: OS

- BSFB exerts the most robust positive influence on OS (Beta = 0.441, very significant p = 0.000).
- HRMCE greatly influences OS (Beta = 0.361, p = 0.000).
- COS does not have a significant impact (p = 0.151) on OS — it has a low t-value, and
 - p-value > 0.05.

Since the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, we accept the hypothesis (H1). Since the p-value (0.000) is significantly less than the 0.05 level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1). This means there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables being tested.

The findings confirm that the performance of JRGB has a statistically significant positive impact on rural financial inclusion and economic development in Jharkhand.

Objective Achieved

The data supports key objectives of assessing JRGB's impact on rural financial inclusion and government initiatives. Regional responses highlight stronger engagement in South Chotanagpur, indicating focused outreach, while other regions need more attention. Branch and ATM availability received mixed reactions, with many

neutral or negative responses, suggesting infrastructure gaps limiting access. Over 66% agree JRGB promotes government financial inclusion schemes like PMJDY and Mudra Yojana, reflecting effective implementation. However, 34.4% disagreed that the loan application process is simple, indicating barriers to credit access. Interest rates on savings accounts drew mostly neutral responses, signalling potential communication or competitiveness issues. Importantly, 71% believe JRGB reduces dependence on informal lenders, confirming progress toward financial inclusion. These insights reveal strengths and areas needing improvement to enhance JRGB's rural banking impact.

The survey results also indicate that JRGB's credit services contribute positively to rural income, with 52.9% of respondents agreeing that these services enhanced their income, supporting the objective of income growth through credit facilitation.

However, 28.9% disagreed, highlighting the need to reassess credit delivery and improve loan utilization support. Regarding agricultural productivity, 50.7% of respondents acknowledged improvement due to JRGB loans, though 39.5% remained neutral, suggesting varied effectiveness and the necessity to better communicate loan benefits to farmers.

Microfinance and rural loans show strong support for small businesses, with 71.7% agreeing on JRGB's role, affirming the objective of promoting rural entrepreneurship. Support for women-led businesses is recognized by 60.15% of respondents, emphasizing progress toward financial inclusion. On customer service, 54.71% found JRGB staff helpful, and 60.9% rated staff attitudes as courteous and professional, though concerns about staffing adequacy (38.8% disagreed) and limited branch/ATM availability remain, indicating infrastructure gaps. Overall, 49.3% expressed satisfaction with JRGB's services, reflecting moderate success but also revealing areas needing improvement to fully achieve the bank's financial inclusion goals.

Findings

The study assessed the performance of Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank (JRGB), revealing that 49.3% of respondents were satisfied with the bank's services, with service quality and human resource management being key drivers of satisfaction. JRGB played a crucial role in advancing financial inclusion through schemes like PMJDY and Mudra Yojana. However, digital banking adoption remained limited due to poor internet connectivity and digital illiteracy, with 51.8% of users expressing neutrality toward usability. While 52.9% acknowledged credit support for income growth, loan transparency and process complexity were concerns. Demographically, the study found higher engagement among middle-aged and older adults, with income and education impacting digital banking use. JRGB's progress in financial inclusion is

notable, but more efforts in digital transformation, service enhancement, and financial literacy are needed to enhance overall rural banking experience.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Jharkhand Rajya Gramin Bank (JRGB) plays a key role in promoting rural financial inclusion, with nearly half of respondents satisfied with its services. However, challenges such as low digital adoption, poor infrastructure, and complicated loan processes hinder its effectiveness. Opportunities lie in digital transformation, financial literacy, and targeted credit programs for underserved groups. To enhance impact, JRGB must improve infrastructure, train staff, simplify services, and tailor strategies to diverse rural needs. Future research should focus on long-term impacts of digital banking and ways to strengthen financial inclusion for sustainable rural development.

Recommendations

To strengthen rural banking, JRGB should expand its branch and ATM network in underserved regions such as Palamu and Kolhan, and make digital platforms more user-friendly for rural and semi-literate customers. Financial and digital literacy programs must target women, the elderly, and low-income communities through mobile vans, local language materials, and community meetings. Simplifying loan processes, offering pre-approved loans, and using AI for risk monitoring will improve credit delivery and reduce NPAs.

Improving customer service through staff training focused on rural needs and digital support is essential. Promoting government schemes like PMJDY and Mudra Yojana and launching specialized products for SHGs and youth entrepreneurs can increase engagement. Regular feedback systems will help track service quality and address gaps.

REFERENCE

1. Ibrahim, M. S. (2010). Performance evaluation of regional rural banks in India. *International Business Research*, 3(4), 203.
2. Chanu, A. I., & Das, S. (2016). A Study on Efficiency of Select Regional Rural Banks in India. *THE INDIAN JOURNAL OF COMMERCE*, 69(4). Ayekam Ibemcha Chanu and Shibu Das
3. Venkatalakshmi, V., & Chandraiah, M. (2016). Current Position of RRBs in India A Review. *BIMS International Journal of Social Science Research*, 1(2), 108-116.
4. Singh, D. B. (2017). An Empirical Study on Regional Rural Banks in India. *Journal of Management Value & Ethics*, 7(4), 4-19.
5. Kanika, N., & Sahni, N. (2013). Financial performance evaluation of RRB's in India. *International Journal of Management & Information Technology*, 4(2), 81-92.
6. Barot, M. B., & Japee, G. (2021). Indian Rural Banking–Role of Regional Rural Banks. *A Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(2), 56-59.
7. Dhanabhakya, M. (2014). Role of regional rural banks in India. Problems and prospects of rural banking and its impact on empowerment of rural household, 12.
8. Krishna, S. H., Kumar, K.G., & Logambal, R. (2022). A study on impact of financial inclusion initiative among rural account holders. *Weser Books*, 1(1), 8.
9. Joshi, V., & Jain, S. C. A Study on the financial performance of the inflow and outflow of funds in regional rural banks
10. Lakra, K., Kushwaha, S., & Singh, H. P. *PATTERN Of Agricultural Credit Supply And Repayment Behaviour Of Tribal Borrowers In Jharkhand* (2015).
11. Rahul Singh Gautam, Jagjeevan Kanoujiya (2022). Role of Regional Rural Banks in Rural Development and Its Influences on Digital Literacy in India.
12. N. Sabitha Devi (2014). Problems and Prospects of Regional Rural Banks in India.
13. Rahul Singh Gautam, Venkata Mrudula Bhimavarapu, Aashi Rawal (2022). Study on Regional Rural Banks and their Impact on Poverty Reduction in India
14. Satish Kumar, Vibhor Goyal, and Poonam Sharma (2017). Performance Evaluation of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in India.
15. Anil Kumar Soni and Abhay Kapre (2011). Performance Evaluation Of Regional Rural Banks In India.
16. Soni, A. K., & Kapre, A. (2013). A Study on Current Status of Regional Rural Banks in India. *National Journal of Research in Commerce and Management*, 2(2), 1-16.
17. Balamuniswamy, D., & Erraiah, G. (2013). Regional rural banks in India: an analysis.
18. Sivaiah, K. (2016). Performance evaluation of regional rural banks in India. *World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(7), 13-18.
19. Soni, A. K., & Kapre, A. (2012). Performance evaluation of regional rural banks in India. *National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research In*, 1(2), 132-144.
20. Kathawala, A. M., & Sharma, V. (2021). A Study on the Performance of Regional Rural Banks in India. *RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 6(11), 28-32.
21. Ahmed, J. U., Bhandari, G. P., & Rohima Ahmed, R. A. (2013). Profitability of Regional Rural Banks in India: an empirical analysis in Meghalaya Rural Bank. *Journal of Rural and Industrial Development Volume*, 1(1).
22. DAS, D. S. (2020). A Fund Componential Analysis: A Study on Regional Rural Banks in North Eastern Region. *Parishodh Journal*, 9(3), 7557-7578.
23. Gautam, R. S., & Kanoujiya, J. (2022). Role of regional rural banks in rural development and its

influences on digital literacy in India. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 5(12), 92-101.

24. Gowda, B. V. P., & Shashi Kumar, T. P. (2024). A Study on Growth and Performance of Regional Rural Bank (KVGB) in Karnataka. *International Journal of Finance Management Economics*, 7(2), 47-54.